

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Ka'ana'ana**FIRST NAME:** Carmen**PROGRAM CODE:** LLM**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: MS Office 365 on Windows 10

ACADEMIC WRITING AND TECHNOLOGY

1) INTRODUCTION

Petroglyphs were painstakingly etched into stone in Hawai'i and similar remnants of ancient writings tattoo the Earth. Since then, people have come a long way in their writing academically and technologically. While advancing from stone, clay, leather, and parchment, to paper and intangible bytes, the means and methods are easier, but the fundamentals of professional international academic writing remain set in structure and in rules. This response paper examines the structure and rules of successful writing, and the aid technology brings to today's international academics.

2) ACADEMIC WRITING & TECHNOLOGY

The transmission of information is the basis of life, and like life, it requires a structure to thrive. In a small world with many cultures, a uniform universal structure serves to highlight the information and communicate it systematically. Structure and rules are the bones of international academic writing and technology is the muscle. The rigorous discipline of research, organization, and writing, was once a tremendous, tedious task, but is now eased and assisted by technology, allowing the exchange of knowledge to accelerate at the incredible rate that the world finds itself caught up in.

a) The Bones of Academic Writing

The bones of academic writing are those rules universally agreed to; flow, form, language, style, tone, thesis, grammar, consistency, arguments, evidence. And most

importantly, giving credit where credit is due. To properly acknowledge that which came before which helped shape what one is offering now. But is that not also a basic human rule? For Hawaiians, what we are is from our ancestors, we are here because of the efforts of those who came before, and so we honor that. “A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers” (EUCLID 2006). A grave breach of international academic writing is not honoring the work of others, by lack of citation or plagiarism.

There is no excuse for either lack of citation or plagiarism. Keeping track of resources and citations among thousands of pages of information, books, and sources, is no longer the arduous undertaking it once was. With programs like Zotero, that organize countless resources and then also properly format, insert, and compile citations, that task of citing is not even a task but an ease. “All academic essays MUST contain references. Referencing guards against plagiarism, a serious academic offence” (EUCLID 2015, 5).

The complexities and copious particulars of the essential rules, formats, and styles such as the *Chicago Manual of Style*, 2003, and *Kate Turabian's Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press), are easily adhered to with the use of technology.

b) The Muscle of Academic Writing

If rules are the bones, then technology is the muscle of professional international academic writing. Technology is lifting the heavy and humdrum work, reducing the banal burdens, and liberating time to produce more content. Euclid University's utilization of technological innovations helps students build a solid foundation for *successful* academic writing at an international level.

i) Grammarly

Grammarly is an essential tool offering grammar and spell checking, plagiarism detection, and services for writers, and its free. It is like a teacher helping along the with the writing process.

ii) Zotero

Zotero is a free bibliographic and research manager that builds a library of resources. It is like a virtual library in your pocket wherever you go, with a librarian to assist.

There is great technology like these programs available to support writers of all levels, and more being developed. Like the academic writing it highlights and supports, this technology is built upon the compilation of innovations of the past to carry us into the future. Philosophically intriguing, these assisting programs are artificial intelligence or AI. “Based on recent developments in the field of Artificial Intelligence and the identified digital capabilities of future universities a change in the basic work of academic research

is predicted”. (Exner-Stöhr et al. 2017) Designed to do our grunt work, AI knows what we know, and grows. “Chuck Williams [Wc83]: ‘Artificial Intelligence is a multidisciplinary field whose goal is to automate activities that presently require human intelligence’” (Exner-Stöhr et al. 2017).

Designed to make life easier, AI also raises strange questions and concerns. Renown theoretical physicist Stephen Hawking warns, “The development of full artificial intelligence could spell the end of the human race” (Cellan-Jones 2014). And an ancient warning from the most iconic writer, that what nourishes me, extinguishes me, 'Quod me alit, me extinguit' (Shakespeare 1608).

These technologies also serve to bring the world more together, to connect us in incredible ways. And because of this, it is important to maintain a uniform and universal format for sharing information. This universal and uniform format helps bridge language and culture to facilitate as efficient communication as possible between people from anywhere in the world.

The challenges of communicating across languages alone is a big one. But one that technology is also tackling, from AI programs that can translate, to providing forums for connecting with human translators anywhere.

Even within the same language, we face challenges communicating, and standards bridge those nuances of meaning. English, for example, has evolved into an international language and into a World English. Originating in England, its use, through commerce and British colonization, spread around the world. Reaching America, English grew as America grew, and American English has come to dominate World English and international relations today (EUCLID 2015, 54).

Irish playwright and wit Oscar Wilde, in 1887 noted in *The Canterville Ghost*, “...she was quite English, and was an excellent example of the fact that we have really everything in common with America nowadays, except, of course, language” (Angmohdan.com, 2015). To make it more confusing, places like Singapore use a mixture of British and American English (British vs American vs Singapore English 2015) which puts the common comma in conundrum, in predicaments of proper positions. Woman: without her, man is nothing. Woman without her man, is nothing. It is vital to learn the correct uses of comma, a fundamental of language, and to consistently apply either the US or UK standard (Try telling that to the Singaporeans!) (EUCLID 2015, 7, 59).

3) CONCLUSION

I did not have to make a clay tablet to write this response paper. Clay tablets have been upgraded to touchscreen tablets, inscribing my words on a more permanent record. Thanks to technology I can focus on writing and let the robots take care of the rules and mechanics. Computers and their programs keep track of form and structure and style and make the grind of academic writing and sharing knowledge easier and more enjoyable. We can spend more time sharing our passions and discovering research instead of organizing

citations and sources and struggling with form and function. The present and future of academic writing lay in its past and its structure, technology carries it forward, and the world comes closer together.

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